

CP1: MtrunA17_Chrc01g0489091_1F_199-492_294_MtrunA17_Chrc01g0489091_3F_384-629_246_-1_iteration_2

CP2: MtrunA17_Chrc28g0493951_2F_422-661_240_MtrunA17_Chrc28g0493951_3F_498-1307_810_-2_iteration_6

CP3: MtrunA17_Chrg0148371_1F_2233-2337_105_MtrunA17_Chrg0148371_3F_198-2927_2730_-1_iteration_16

CP4: MtrunA17_Chrg0149991_2F_1847-2362_516_MtrunA17_Chrg0149991_3F_171-1910_1740_+2_iteration_0

CP5: MtrunA17_Chrg0150571_3F_1035-1250_216_MtrunA17_Chrg0150571_2F_224-1192_969_-2_iteration_15

CP6: MtrunA17_Ch1g0152521_2F_290-436_147_MtrunA17_Ch1g0152521_1F_1-969_969_-2_iteration_20

MS peptide 6 N14Se
CP6

CP7: MtrunA17_Ch1g0153001_1F_178-519_342_MtrunA17_Ch1g0153001_3F_396-806_411_-1_iteration_9

MS peptide 7 N10
CP7

CP8: MtrunA17_Ch1g0155251_1F_1228-1467_240_MtrunA17_Ch1g0155251_3F_138-2090_1953_-1_iteration_16

MS peptide 8 L
CP8

CP9: MtrunA17_Ch1g0158341_2F_758-859_102_MtrunA17_Ch1g0158341_1F_1-1251_1251_+2_iteration_17

MS peptide 9 W
CP9

CP10: MtrunA17_Ch1g0162101_3F_3-221_219_MtrunA17_Ch1g0162101_1F_1-255_255_+2_iteration_1

MS peptide 10 BF
CP10

CP11: MtrunA17_Ch1g0164591_3F_3-338_336_MtrunA17_Ch1g0164591_2F_314-1369_1056_-1_iteration_2

MS peptide 11 R
CP11

-1 (3a→2r)

mRNA
3,657

CP12: MtrunA17_Ch1g0178361_1F_529-618_90_MtrunA17_Ch1g0178361_3F_201-1124_924_-1_iteration_9

MS peptide 12 N10
CP12

-1 (1a→3r)

mRNA
1,437

CP13: MtrunA17_Ch1g0181761_1F_445-570_126_MtrunA17_Ch1g0181761_3F_18-1262_1245_+2_iteration_0

MS peptide 13 N10W
CP13

+2 (1a→3r)

mRNA
1,585

CP14: MtrunA17_Ch1g0182591_1F_4162-4257_96_MtrunA17_Ch1g0182591_2F_11-4228_4218_-1_iteration_11

MS peptide 14 F
CP14

-1 (2r→1a)

mRNA
4,258

CP15: MtrunA17_Ch1g0183001_1F_2749-2943_195_MtrunA17_Ch1g0183001_3F_375-4916_4542_-2_iteration_16

MS peptide 15 N10
CP15

-2 (3r→1a)

mRNA
5,389

CP16: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811_1F_535-621_87_MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811_2F_2-1774_1773_+1_iteration_10

MS peptide 16 Se
CP16

CP17: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811_1F_535-621_87_MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811_2F_2-1774_1773_+1_iteration_2

MS peptide 17 Se
CP17

CP18: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811_1F_535-621_87_MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811_2F_2-1774_1773_+1_iteration_9

MS peptide 18 Se
CP18

CP19: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185871_1F_1447-1602_156_MtrunA17_Chr1g0185871_3F_309-3371_3063_-2_iteration_3

MS peptide 19 RoCRoDPD
CP19

CP20: MtrunA17_Chr1g0190571_2F_62-262_201_MtrunA17_Chr1g0190571_1F_1-2274_2274_+2_iteration_10

MS peptide 20 Se
CP20

CP21: MtrunA17_Chr1g0191411_1F_1660-1869_210_MtrunA17_Chr1g0191411_2F_1601-1732_132_+2_iteration_22

MS peptide 21 St
CP21

LIGSDCHINFDPVQIQSMTLASSTLQIR **RHVIRDLNIIIC**
altProt 1 altProt 2

CP22: MtrunA17_Chr1g0198091_3F_255-443_189_MtrunA17_Chr1g0198091_1F_379-507_129_+1_iteration_2

MS peptide 22 W
CP22

LGPOWSNRELENSMK
altProt **LGPOWSNRELENSMK** YTESMVEIGKKVATTIRKRSIEMVE
refProt

CP23: MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071_3F_828-1001_174_MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071_2F_218-1567_1350_+2_iteration_1

MS peptide 23 L
CP23

LOTSPSDYHERVYKIGGIGTVPVGR
altProt **LOTSPSDYHERVYKIGGIGTVPVGR** VETGVIKPGMVVTF A
refProt

CP24: MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071_3F_828-1001_174_MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071_2F_218-1567_1350_-2_iteration_11

MS peptide 24 Se
CP24

PISGFEGDNMIERS **STNLDWYKR**
refProt **STNLDWYKR** VQPFLRPLTKSMSLRGLQT
altProt

CP25: MtrunA17_Chr1g0202001_2F_149-421_273_MtrunA17_Chr1g0202001_1F_1-2331_2331_-1_iteration_0

MS peptide 25 N10N14
CP25

EFNATFK **LVMVQSLLDLHGSYRRR**
altProt **LVMVQSLLDLHGSYRRR** LFGEINPSITELQHLTYL
refProt

CP26: MtrunA17_Ch1g0205601_3F_321-395_75_MtrunA17_Ch1g0205601_1F_13-369_357_-1_iteration_17

MS peptide 26 FR
CP26

CP27: MtrunA17_Ch1g0207811_1F_1462-1824_363_MtrunA17_Ch1g0207811_3F_207-1913_1707_+1_iteration_19

MS peptide 27 L
CP27

CP28: MtrunA17_Ch1g0207921_2F_260-391_132_MtrunA17_Ch1g0207921_1F_1-597_597_+1_iteration_6

MS peptide 28 N10N14
CP28

CP29: MtrunA17_Ch1g0209791_2F_2-130_129_MtrunA17_Ch1g0209791_1F_1-288_288_+2_iteration_5

MS peptide 29 Se
CP29

CP30: MtrunA17_Ch1g0210521_2F_782-928_147_MtrunA17_Ch1g0210521_3F_192-917_726_-1_iteration_23

MS peptide 30 N10
CP30

CP31: MtrunA17_Chr1g0212961_2F_617-703_87_MtrunA17_Chr1g0212961_3F_63-1136_1074_-2_iteration_2

MS peptide 31 FL
CP31

mRNA
1,487

CP32: MtrunA17_Chr1g1004575_2F_299-379_81_MtrunA17_Chr1g1004575_3F_333-416_84_-2_iteration_11

MS peptide 32 PD
CP32

ncRNA
523

CP33: MtrunA17_Chr2g0283311_1F_766-849_84_MtrunA17_Chr2g0283311_2F_263-868_606_-2_iteration_14

MS peptide 33 R
CP33

mRNA
1,691

CP34: MtrunA17_Chr2g0285461_2F_1553-1795_243_MtrunA17_Chr2g0285461_1F_838-3573_2736_+2_iteration_0

MS peptide 34 N14
CP34

mRNA
4,359

CP35: MtrunA17_Chr2g0292921_2F_1202-1453_252_MtrunA17_Chr2g0292921_1F_187-1545_1359_-2_iteration_6

MS peptide 35 Se
CP35

mRNA
1,942

CP36: MtrunA17_Ch2g0298731_1F_3127-3255_129_MtrunA17_Ch2g0298731_3F_105-3674_3570_-1_iteration_7

MS peptide 36 St
CP36

CP37: MtrunA17_Ch2g0299561_2F_3347-3535_189_MtrunA17_Ch2g0299561_1F_97-3969_3873_-1_iteration_17

MS peptide 37 N10
CP37

CP38: MtrunA17_Ch2g0304891_3F_627-725_99_MtrunA17_Ch2g0304891_1F_643-1512_870_-2_iteration_1

MS peptide 38 W
CP38

CP39: MtrunA17_Ch2g0305951_3F_3-113_111_MtrunA17_Ch2g0305951_1F_1-153_153_-1_iteration_14

MS peptide 39 N14
CP39

CP40: MtrunA17_Ch2g0309251_1F_1300-1383_84_MtrunA17_Ch2g0309251_3F_795-2144_1350_-1_iteration_5

MS peptide 40 B
CP40

CP41: MtrunA17_Chr2g0310041_3F_3-95_93_MtrunA17_Chr2g0310041_1F_1-540_540_-2_iteration_20

MS peptide 41 RoC
CP41

CP42: MtrunA17_Chr2g0312631_1F_2020-2094_75_MtrunA17_Chr2g0312631_3F_213-3398_3186_+2_iteration_11

MS peptide 42 L
CP42

CP43: MtrunA17_Chr2g0316291_3F_1647-1745_99_MtrunA17_Chr2g0316291_2F_101-3394_3294_-2_iteration_1

MS peptide 43 W
CP43

CP44: MtrunA17_Chr2g0326801_1F_2404-2493_90_MtrunA17_Chr2g0326801_3F_2394-2507_114_-2_iteration_19

MS peptide 44 N10
CP44

CP45: MtrunA17_Chr2g0328091_3F_87-245_159_MtrunA17_Chr2g0328091_2F_107-1243_1137_-1_iteration_5

MS peptide 45 F
CP45

CP46: MtrunA17_Chr2g0329031_3F_1209-1379_171_MtrunA17_Chr2g0329031_2F_197-2440_2244_+2_iteration_20

MS peptide 46 B
CP46

DGGSWLIGLNLLEMLSGFK **PCMMIVHVGCRMK** DISLAGLS
altProt refProt

CP47: MtrunA17_Chr3g0079521_2F_1580-1747_168_MtrunA17_Chr3g0079521_1F_25-2292_2268_-1_iteration_10

MS peptide 47 St
CP47

TTNIFQAQERFWILQKYR **RTLFEYYAWDYR** VLKTFARHYS T
altProt refProt

CP48: MtrunA17_Chr3g0083801_1F_76-174_99_MtrunA17_Chr3g0083801_3F_12-737_726_+1_iteration_3

MS peptide 48 N10
CP48

FFFVLVK **MAMIENETKQEANVWFVYAMK** KATLKP FVTSNA
refProt altProt

CP49: MtrunA17_Chr3g0091141_1F_976-1071_96_MtrunA17_Chr3g0091141_2F_170-1891_1722_-2_iteration_11

MS peptide 49 B
CP49

LLQCTWRIRITVWHYNK **SKNLALEPAPT MVK** WIRVLYSDFTA
altProt refProt

CP50: MtrunA17_Chr3g0091671_2F_14-130_117_MtrunA17_Chr3g0091671_1F_1-153_153_-2_iteration_14

MS peptide 50 PD
CP50

NPVDHPHGGGEGRAPIGVEK
MNPVDHPHGGGEGRAPIGVEK NPQLLG VILHLEE E
refProt altProt

CP51: MtrunA17_Chr3g0096421_3F_54-173_120_MtrunA17_Chr3g0096421_1F_46-1086_1041_-1_iteration_7

MS peptide 51 Se
CP51

mRNA
1,440

CP52: MtrunA17_Chr3g0100221_2F_803-922_120_MtrunA17_Chr3g0100221_1F_34-852_819_+1_iteration_6

MS peptide 52 R
CP52

mRNA
922

CP53: MtrunA17_Chr3g0102171_2F_236-379_144_MtrunA17_Chr3g0102171_1F_73-3423_3351_-2_iteration_5

MS peptide 53 Se
CP53

mRNA
3,997

CP54: MtrunA17_Chr3g0105981_2F_1454-1618_165_MtrunA17_Chr3g0105981_3F_27-1478_1452_-1_iteration_5

MS peptide 54 N14BSe
CP54

mRNA
1,894

CP55: MtrunA17_Chr3g0110451_1F_538-711_174_MtrunA17_Chr3g0110451_2F_620-886_267_-2_iteration_4

MS peptide 55 PhC
CP55

mRNA
910

CP56: MtrunA17_Chr3g0113591_2F_1295-1465_171_MtrunA17_Chr3g0113591_1F_124-2748_2625_-2_iteration_19

MS peptide 56 L
CP56

CP57: MtrunA17_Chr3g0124631_2F_1127-1249_123_MtrunA17_Chr3g0124631_1F_130-2304_2175_+2_iteration_19

MS peptide 57 F
CP57

CP58: MtrunA17_Chr3g0127321_2F_1055-1303_249_MtrunA17_Chr3g0127321_1F_1-1329_1329_+2_iteration_18

MS peptide 58 RoC
CP58

CP59: MtrunA17_Chr3g0130671_3F_1026-1190_165_MtrunA17_Chr3g0130671_1F_334-1179_846_-1_iteration_5

MS peptide 59 N10
CP59

CP60: MtrunA17_Chr3g0135761_2F_734-958_225_MtrunA17_Chr3g0135761_1F_1-2115_2115_+2_iteration_0

MS peptide 60 Se
CP60

CP61: MtrunA17_Chr3g0137391_3F_915-1070_156_MtrunA17_Chr3g0137391_2F_23-1768_1746_-1_iteration_8

MS peptide 61 B
CP61

CP62: MtrunA17_Chr3g0141901_2F_1316-1585_270_MtrunA17_Chr3g0141901_1F_70-1371_1302_-2_iteration_17

MS peptide 62 N10N14BFSeWRoCPCPD
CP62

CP63: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151_1F_1222-1311_90_MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151_3F_33-1415_1383_+2_iteration_3

MS peptide 63 L
CP63

CP64: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151_1F_1222-1311_90_MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151_3F_33-1415_1383_-1_iteration_5

MS peptide 64 FLStWPCPD
CP64

CP65: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151_1F_1222-1311_90_MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151_3F_33-1415_1383_-1_iteration_6

MS peptide 65 LStW
CP65

CP66: MtrunA17_Chr3g1011650_2F_26-340_315_MtrunA17_Chr3g1011650_3F_108-224_117_-2_iteration_2

MS peptide 66 RoC
CP66

CP67: MtrunA17_Chr4g0000131_1F_1471-1644_174_MtrunA17_Chr4g0000131_3F_159-2459_2301_+1_iteration_7

MS peptide 67 N10
CP67

CP68: MtrunA17_Chr4g0000891_3F_3-473_471_MtrunA17_Chr4g0000891_1F_1-471_471_+2_iteration_6

MS peptide 68 N14
CP68

CP69: MtrunA17_Chr4g0004721_1F_634-813_180_MtrunA17_Chr4g0004721_3F_171-1157_987_+1_iteration_9

MS peptide 69 N10
CP69

CP70: MtrunA17_Chr4g0014251_3F_45-242_198_MtrunA17_Chr4g0014251_1F_1-327_327_+1_iteration_4

MS peptide 70 N10
CP70

CP71: MtrunA17_Chr4g0022491_3F_762-923_162_MtrunA17_Chr4g0022491_2F_413-1177_765_+2_iteration_9

MS peptide 71 W
CP71

CP72: MtrunA17_Chr4g0023791_1F_1-84_84_MtrunA17_Chr4g0023791_2F_2-82_81_-1_iteration_5

MS peptide 72 F
CP72

CP73: MtrunA17_Chr4g0034271_3F_15-344_330_MtrunA17_Chr4g0034271_1F_1-738_738_-1_iteration_7

MS peptide 73 PD
CP73

CP74: MtrunA17_Chr4g0034491_2F_1151-1708_558_MtrunA17_Chr4g0034491_1F_88-2415_2328_-2_iteration_1

MS peptide 74 F
CP74

CP75: MtrunA17_Chr4g0037381_1F_880-1014_135_MtrunA17_Chr4g0037381_2F_422-1024_603_-1_iteration_16

MS peptide 75 B
CP75

CP76: MtrunA17_Chr4g0040471_3F_2295-2474_180_MtrunA17_Chr4g0040471_1F_85-2868_2784_-1_iteration_14

MS peptide 76 N10N14FLRSeSt
CP76

CP77: MtrunA17_Chr4g0055331_2F_62-127_66_MtrunA17_Chr4g0055331_1F_1-738_738_+2_iteration_9

MS peptide 77 B
CP77

CP78: MtrunA17_Chr4g0059001_2F_83-277_195_MtrunA17_Chr4g0059001_1F_1-840_840_-2_iteration_11

MS peptide 78 B
CP78

CP79: MtrunA17_Chr4g0063201_2F_446-535_90_MtrunA17_Chr4g0063201_1F_262-522_261_-2_iteration_18

MS peptide 79 Se
CP79

CP80: MtrunA17_Chr4g0070011_3F_1743-1832_90_MtrunA17_Chr4g0070011_1F_58-2481_2424_-1_iteration_16

MS peptide 80 N14R
CP80

CP81: MtrunA17_Ch5g0393401_2F_1649-1765_117_MtrunA17_Ch5g0393401_3F_282-1781_1500_-2_iteration_10

MS peptide 81 N10F
CP81

CP82: MtrunA17_Ch5g0400181_1F_859-1017_159_MtrunA17_Ch5g0400181_3F_312-2192_1881_+1_iteration_14

MS peptide 82 PD
CP82

CP83: MtrunA17_Ch5g0405061_2F_182-412_231_MtrunA17_Ch5g0405061_3F_228-2174_1947_-2_iteration_20

MS peptide 83 N10
CP83

CP84: MtrunA17_Ch5g0408581_2F_2615-2860_246_MtrunA17_Ch5g0408581_1F_1-3168_3168_-2_iteration_12

MS peptide 84 RoC
CP84

CP85: MtrunA17_Ch5g0415031_1F_931-1152_222_MtrunA17_Ch5g0415031_3F_114-4400_4287_+1_iteration_19

MS peptide 85 L
CP85

CP86: MtrunA17_Chr5g0415911_1F_3553-3948_396_MtrunA17_Chr5g0415911_3F_2832-3632_801_-2_iteration_6

MS peptide 86 N10
CP86

CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761_2F_1835-1918_84_MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761_3F_1818-1925_108_-1_iteration_4

MS peptide 87 Se
CP87

CP88: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291_2F_3056-3259_204_MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291_3F_3120-3197_78_-1_iteration_5

MS peptide 88 B
CP88

CP89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291_2F_4808-5617_810_MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291_1F_4921-5037_117_-1_iteration_29

MS peptide 89 PhC
CP89

CP90: MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341_2F_2501-2623_123_MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341_3F_2298-2531_234_+2_iteration_3

MS peptide 90 L
CP90

CP91: MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341_3F_1059-1172_114_MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341_1F_1-1620_1620_-2_iteration_9

MS peptide 91 W
CP91

CP92: MtrunA17_Chr5g0431401_3F_1149-1388_240_MtrunA17_Chr5g0431401_2F_2-1354_1353_+1_iteration_18

MS peptide 92 RSt
CP92

CP93: MtrunA17_Chr5g0435191_1F_883-1032_150_MtrunA17_Chr5g0435191_2F_677-979_303_-1_iteration_25

MS peptide 93 Se
CP93

CP94: MtrunA17_Chr5g0444231_2F_758-967_210_MtrunA17_Chr5g0444231_3F_3-902_900_+2_iteration_11

MS peptide 94 F
CP94

CP95: MtrunA17_Chr6g0451601_2F_434-577_144_MtrunA17_Chr6g0451601_1F_91-543_453_-2_iteration_29

MS peptide 95 F
CP95

CP96: MtrunA17_Chrg0452781_3F_4245-4397_153_MtrunA17_Chrg0452781_1F_1-4458_4458_-1_iteration_15

MS peptide 96 F
CP96

mRNA
5,917

CP97: MtrunA17_Chrg0457351_1F_406-636_231_MtrunA17_Chrg0457351_3F_279-575_297_-2_iteration_22

MS peptide 97 RoD
CP97

-2 (3a1→1a2)
*

mRNA
2,114

CP98: MtrunA17_Chrg0457461_3F_438-596_159_MtrunA17_Chrg0457461_2F_170-715_546_+2_iteration_6

MS peptide 98 B
CP98

+2 (3a→2r)
*

mRNA
946

CP99: MtrunA17_Chrg0457461_3F_438-596_159_MtrunA17_Chrg0457461_2F_170-715_546_-2_iteration_17

MS peptide 99 BSeW
CP99

-2 (2r→3a)
*

mRNA
946

CP100: MtrunA17_Chrg0457461_3F_438-596_159_MtrunA17_Chrg0457461_2F_170-715_546_-2_iteration_18

MS peptide 100 BWPCPD
CP100

-2 (2r→3a)
*

mRNA
946

CP101: MtrunA17_Chr6g0458091_1F_1240-1362_123_MtrunA17_Chr6g0458091_2F_275-1621_1347_-2_iteration_4

MS peptide 101 N10N14Se
CP101

CP102: MtrunA17_Chr6g0459481_3F_183-263_81_MtrunA17_Chr6g0459481_1F_1-363_363_-1_iteration_12

MS peptide 102 L
CP102

CP103: MtrunA17_Chr6g0461931_3F_234-497_264_MtrunA17_Chr6g0461931_2F_86-298_213_+1_iteration_7

MS peptide 103 PC
CP103

CP104: MtrunA17_Chr6g0462271_3F_3-149_147_MtrunA17_Chr6g0462271_1F_1-180_180_+1_iteration_5

MS peptide 104 W
CP104

CP105: MtrunA17_Chr6g0468411_3F_408-509_102_MtrunA17_Chr6g0468411_1F_1-507_507_+2_iteration_28

MS peptide 105 Se
CP105

CP106: MtrunA17_Chr6g0476751_3F_2274-2426_153_MtrunA17_Chr6g0476751_2F_359-2653_2295_+2_iteration_5

MS peptide 106 R
CP106

CP107: MtrunA17_Chr6g0479001_1F_3799-3981_183_MtrunA17_Chr6g0479001_2F_3701-3817_117_+2_iteration_5

MS peptide 107 PD
CP107

CP108: MtrunA17_Chr6g0485321_1F_1768-1881_114_MtrunA17_Chr6g0485321_3F_1674-1892_219_+2_iteration_13

MS peptide 108 R
CP108

CP109: MtrunA17_Chr6g0486961_3F_1875-2120_246_MtrunA17_Chr6g0486961_1F_1-2943_2943_-2_iteration_12

MS peptide 109 Se
CP109

CP110: MtrunA17_Chr7g0214741_1F_340-462_123_MtrunA17_Chr7g0214741_3F_132-1478_1347_+1_iteration_8

MS peptide 110 Se
CP110

CP111: MtrunA17_Chr7g0214911_3F_183-368_186_MtrunA17_Chr7g0214911_2F_140-1999_1860_-2_iteration_6

MS peptide 111 Se
CP111

-2 (2r→3a)
*

CP112: MtrunA17_Chr7g0219691_1F_1507-1602_96_MtrunA17_Chr7g0219691_3F_12-2699_2688_-2_iteration_2

MS peptide 112 F
CP112

-2 (3r→1a)
*

CP113: MtrunA17_Chr7g0221631_3F_3-125_123_MtrunA17_Chr7g0221631_1F_1-351_351_-1_iteration_13

MS peptide 113 B
CP113

-1 (1r→3a)
*

CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401_2F_2402-2755_354_MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401_3F_2268-2465_198_+2_iteration_1

MS peptide 114 RoD
CP114

+2 (3a1→2a2)
*

CP115: MtrunA17_Chr7g0230341_2F_2-307_306_MtrunA17_Chr7g0230341_1F_16-186_171_-1_iteration_3

MS peptide 115 N10
CP115

-1 (2a→1r)
*

CP116: MtrunA17_Chr7g0232851_1F_502-684_183_MtrunA17_Chr7g0232851_2F_587-775_189_-2_iteration_22

MS peptide 116 N10
CP116

mRNA
991

CP117: MtrunA17_Chr7g0237331_2F_1172-1372_201_MtrunA17_Chr7g0237331_1F_88-2508_2421_+2_iteration_18

MS peptide 117 PC
CP117

mRNA
2,763

CP118: MtrunA17_Chr7g0251971_3F_3-161_159_MtrunA17_Chr7g0251971_1F_1-189_189_-1_iteration_4

MS peptide 118 St
CP118

mRNA
192

CP119: MtrunA17_Chr7g0259611_2F_185-292_108_MtrunA17_Chr7g0259611_3F_201-779_579_-2_iteration_6

MS peptide 119 N10
CP119

mRNA
1,090

CP120: MtrunA17_Chr7g0262821_3F_1662-1847_186_MtrunA17_Chr7g0262821_2F_86-2131_2046_-1_iteration_13

MS peptide 120 Se
CP120

mRNA
2,670

CP121: MtrunA17_Chr7g0270811_3F_1536-1718_183_MtrunA17_Chr7g0270811_2F_8-1711_1704_-2_iteration_10

MS peptide 121 N14BSe
CP121

CP122: MtrunA17_Chr7g1034306_1F_502-681_180_MtrunA17_Chr7g1034306_2F_533-703_171_-2_iteration_17

MS peptide 122 Se
CP122

CP123: MtrunA17_Chr8g0338111_1F_436-534_99_MtrunA17_Chr8g0338111_2F_476-733_258_-2_iteration_11

MS peptide 123 Se
CP123

CP124: MtrunA17_Chr8g0338301_2F_1574-1681_108_MtrunA17_Chr8g0338301_1F_1-1680_1680_+1_iteration_17

MS peptide 124 Se
CP124

CP125: MtrunA17_Chr8g0339891_2F_998-1174_177_MtrunA17_Chr8g0339891_3F_426-1067_642_+2_iteration_11

MS peptide 125 W
CP125

CP126: MtrunA17_Chr8g0342881_2F_656-892_237_MtrunA17_Chr8g0342881_1F_94-2667_2574_-2_iteration_1

MS peptide 126 PD
CP126

CP127: MtrunA17_Chr8g0345421_3F_2838-2963_126_MtrunA17_Chr8g0345421_2F_83-3610_3528_-2_iteration_6

MS peptide 127 LSt
CP127

CP128: MtrunA17_Chr8g0353711_2F_110-283_174_MtrunA17_Chr8g0353711_1F_1-282_282_+1_iteration_21

MS peptide 128 L
CP128

CP129: MtrunA17_Chr8g0355501_1F_1552-1761_210_MtrunA17_Chr8g0355501_3F_63-1898_1836_-2_iteration_6

MS peptide 129 N14
CP129

CP130: MtrunA17_Chr8g0356581_1F_1387-1464_78_MtrunA17_Chr8g0356581_2F_1394-1516_123_+1_iteration_5

MS peptide 130 R
CP130

CP131: MtrunA17_Chr8g0365341_2F_773-1216_444_MtrunA17_Chr8g0365341_1F_169-2331_2163_+2_iteration_7

MS peptide 131 B
CP131

CP132: MtrunA17_Chr8g0368731_2F_1343-1540_198_MtrunA17_Chr8g0368731_1F_1-1875_1875_+1_iteration_0

MS peptide 132 PC
CP132

CP133: MtrunA17_Chr8g0368931_1F_889-1059_171_MtrunA17_Chr8g0368931_3F_3-1043_1041_-2_iteration_12

MS peptide 133 Se
CP133

CP134: MtrunA17_Chr8g0371281_3F_696-851_156_MtrunA17_Chr8g0371281_2F_122-955_834_-2_iteration_4

MS peptide 134 N10
CP134

CP135: MtrunA17_Chr8g0371741_1F_691-888_198_MtrunA17_Chr8g0371741_3F_189-794_606_+1_iteration_16

MS peptide 135 L
CP135

CP136: MtrunA17_Chr8g0373091_1F_457-702_246_MtrunA17_Chr8g0373091_3F_234-1106_873_+1_iteration_3

MS peptide 136 F
CP136

CP137: MtrunA17_Chr8g0376411_1F_433-582_150_MtrunA17_Chr8g0376411_3F_156-1463_1308_-1_iteration_6

MS peptide 137 BF
CP137

CP138: MtrunA17_Chr8g0377071_2F_1406-1693_288_MtrunA17_Chr8g0377071_1F_511-2715_2205_-1_iteration_17

MS peptide 138 L
CP138

CP139: MtrunA17_Chr8g0385331_1F_1456-1719_264_MtrunA17_Chr8g0385331_3F_255-1670_1416_-2_iteration_8

MS peptide 139 B
CP139

CP140: MtrunA17_Chr8g0392351_3F_96-272_177_MtrunA17_Chr8g0392351_1F_1-105_105_+2_iteration_4

MS peptide 140 PD
CP140

CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331_2F_584-874_291_MtrunA17_CPg0492331_3F_603-704_102_-1_iteration_19

MS peptide 141 LSt
CP141

-1 (3a2→2a1)

CP142: MtrunA17_CPg0492381_1F_631-750_120_MtrunA17_CPg0492381_2F_671-820_150_+1_iteration_1

MS peptide 142 N14
CP142

+1 (1a1→2a2)

CP143: MtrunA17_CPg0492461_1F_3232-3426_195_MtrunA17_CPg0492461_3F_1413-7163_5751_+1_iteration_12

MS peptide 143 F
CP143

+1 (3r→1a)

CP144: MtrunA17_CPg0492851_2F_209-328_120_MtrunA17_CPg0492851_3F_129-1157_1029_+1_iteration_6

MS peptide 144 FPD
CP144

+1 (2a→3r)

CP145: MtrunA17_CPg0492941_3F_825-947_123_MtrunA17_CPg0492941_1F_31-1572_1542_-1_iteration_2

MS peptide 145 N14BFLSeWPCPD
CP145

-1 (1r→3a)

CP146: MtrunA17_CPg0493291_1F_733-804_72_MtrunA17_CPg0493291_2F_698-799_102_+2_iteration_18

MS peptide 146 PD
CP146

CP147: MtrunA17_CPg0493401_2F_1223-1450_228_MtrunA17_CPg0493401_3F_261-1778_1518_-2_iteration_7

MS peptide 147 L
CP147

CP148: MtrunA17_MTg0490471_2F_1031-1147_117_MtrunA17_MTg0490471_1F_220-1740_1521_+1_iteration_7

MS peptide 148 Se
CP148

CP149: MtrunA17_MTg0490471_2F_422-538_117_MtrunA17_MTg0490471_1F_220-1740_1521_+1_iteration_16

MS peptide 149 N10N14FLSe
CP149

CP150: MtrunA17_MTg0490971_2F_1562-1699_138_MtrunA17_MTg0490971_3F_1542-1727_186_+1_iteration_12

MS peptide 150 St
CP150

CP151: MtrunA17_MTg0490971_2F_476-628_153_MtrunA17_MTg0490971_1F_277-534_258_+1_iteration_0

MS peptide 151 W
CP151

CTYSLYDK **QVMGPVRRGERNGSSSHFSPQPPK** LKRNRGTLQ
altProt 1 altProt 2

+1 (1a1→2a2)
*

ncRNA
6,062

CP152: MtrunA17_MTg0491151_1F_4534-4659_126_MtrunA17_MTg0491151_2F_4511-4612_102_+2_iteration_15

MS peptide 152 Se
CP152

AAMVRAGKHGHCIGGR **RSAFYLFER** SYVRPTSHRIRGT
altProt 1 altProt 2

+2 (2a1→1a2)
*

ncRNA
6,042

CP153: MtrunA17_MTg0491291_2F_1358-1447_90_MtrunA17_MTg0491291_3F_1329-1421_93_-1_iteration_18

MS peptide 153 B
CP153

SDPLSHAFLRAFGYATSHSRLSRCLR **WMGMPLAVLALIYP**
altProt 1 altProt 2

-1 (3a1→2a2)
*

mRNA
1,982

CP154: MtrunA17_MTg0491501_1F_661-825_165_MtrunA17_MTg0491501_3F_624-734_111_-2_iteration_6

MS peptide 154 PC
CP154

MNLSR **WKKGIAMDSYEK** HSGTRRFNR TTNSYVVQGNKRSAS
altProt 1 altProt 2

-2 (3a1→1a2)
*

ncRNA
5,261

CP155: MtrunA17_MTg0491621_1F_1660-1836_177_MtrunA17_MTg0491621_3F_1377-1772_396_+1_iteration_16

MS peptide 155 N10
CP155

SAPIRIKGS LAFARSREILR **VLRPRFIAAAIWFTGTTK** S
altProt 1 altProt 2

+1 (3a1→1a2)
*

ncRNA
2,110

CP156: MtrunA17_MTg0491711_1F_2815-2910_96_MtrunA17_MTg0491711_3F_2664-2906_243_+1_iteration_24

MS peptide 156 L
CP156

S L L L R K T I P L N E K H A L L R I R E Y K K K **R E I T D W T T K T G R P I**
altProt 1 altProt 2

+1 (3a1→1a2)

ncRNA
5,613

Supplementary Dataset S2. A graphical summary on alignments between 156 chimeric peptide models (CPs) and corresponding MS peptides (left) together with transcript models (right) that feature the transcript type, length in nucleotides, and relative positions of ORFs (to scale) involved in the production of CPs. Reference ORFs (refORFs) and reference proteins (refProts) are shown in yellow. Alternative ORFs (altORFs) and alternative proteins (altProts) are shown in pink. The first in-frame start codon (AUG) in each refORF is marked with a green triangle. If an altORF and a refORF are in the same frame, they are shown in the same level (e.g. CP7). If they are in different reading frames, they are shown in different levels (e.g. CP21). Codes of CPs modeled with MS-supported altProts are shown in a bold font. Codes of CPs with “confident” MS peptide detection in at least one sample are underlined. “Confident” is not the same as validated. For a short chimeric model sequence (mostly 40 amino acids or shorter in our dataset), it is very difficult to receive the status "confident" due to the nature of the MS method. Transcript models also show the positions and characteristics of programmed ribosomal frameshifting (PRF) events, which are mapped with an asterisk. The description of a PRF event should be interpreted as follows. For example, CP1, -1 (1a1→3a2): a minus 1 frameshift changes the translation from frame 1 to frame 3, which corresponds to the change from altORF1 to altORF2. An altORF1 in this study is defined as the one that starts earlier than an altORF2. Switches from altORF2 to altORF1 are also found in this dataset but are five times less frequent (e.g. CP108 and four other CPs). Throughout this study, unique numbers are assigned to chimeric models and their matching chimeric MS peptides. MS peptide identifiers also contain codes of biological samples in which they were detected. For example, the chimeric MS peptide of CP3 was identified in nodules of two developmental stages (10 and 14 days post inoculation). Thus, the identifier of MS peptide 3 ends with “N10N14”.